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Editorial Comments

The Society for Psychology in Sport and Human Behaviour has come a long way in meeting the needs regularly demanded by motivated readership as its 20th volume, and Second edition, 2018 of the African Journal of Cross—Cultural Psychology and Sport Facilitation (AJCPSF) can now have continuous page—numbering effective from its last edition. The current senior is coming with a bang and has varied and interesting articles. The AJCPSF is accessible through the ajol web site online ([http: www.ajolljournal](http://www.ajolljournal)). The Journal e-mail: crsscltrpsychlgy@ahoo.co.uk).

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Or

Adams, W.U.C (1999). Psychological Underpinnings. In R. O. Maxwell, T.W.Y.Dwaflin, and U.K.I. Bills (Eds), Annual Review of Psychotherapy Vol.12, pp.3456).Lagos-Nigeria: Evans

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Counselling Implication of Tourism and Leisure for Healthy Living in Nigeria

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Abstract

The importance of tourism and leisure in the lives of the average majority of Nigerians is not so much articulated and known. Even though the psycho-emotional benefits are well appreciated within the global wellness programme, the paper however discussed the roles of counselling in promoting tourism and leisure among individuals in the Sub-Saharan African region. Guidance and counseling programme offers multi-dimensional services that cater for the in-and of-school needs and generally, the family, industrial settings, socio-economic spheres, hospital and in politics for mediating human holism as precursor to individual and the collective adjustment of persons in the workplace, school and the family. The paper thus highlighted the modus-operandi and vivendi for tourism and leisure, their types and eventual benefits where its practice becomes the vogue.

Keywords: Tourism, Leisure, Healthy living, counselling implication, Nigeria.

Introduction

The continuous chase of basic needs and wants has almost excluded the concept of tourism, Leisure and recreational activities from the minds of Nigerians. We tend to work for nearly twenty-four (24) hours a day and tend to forget the dangers inherent in over-flogging our bodies including our brains with unfathomable stress. According to Denga (2008), stress is perceived as the silent killer which continues to take a toll on our lives. This is because we worked round the clock daily without recourse to the slightest recreational activities. Denga then concluded by saying

that “human being hardly lives to enjoy the fruit of his/her labour to which everyone has voluntarily sentenced themselves (Denga, 2008).

The concepts of tourism and leisure are as old as human Beings; although many Nigerians do not still understand the meaning of tourism, leisure and recreation. According to Suleiman (2016), many Nigerians just partake in leisure activities without knowing what they are or the scientific health benefits derived from them. However, tourism, leisure and recreation goes together; and while tourism is the visit from place to place in friendly and generous behaviour towards their intension, people visit places that are hospitably. Nigerians mostly tour and partake in leisure activities in All-jean Traditional ways by moving from village to different locality to celebrate and recreate before the coming of colonial masters to Nigeria. For instance, through celebration of agricultural seasons, harvesting of crops (as it were the case in new yarn festivals), crowning after additional rulers as the obas, chiefs, emirs, ochi-doma and the tor-tiv, people usually would travel from their own environment to the place where the events are happening to recreate and celebrate. It is still happening in Nigeria setting. The movement of these people from their own place to another place of celebration is refers to as tourism for leisure and to recreate in hospitable manxer, friendly and generous behaviour towards visitors.

However, Suleirnan (2016), added that, before the invasion of Nigeria by the colonial masters, activities such as local wrestling, hunting, masquerade dance, Fulani festival activities, naming and marriage ceremonies archery, swimming contests, horse-racing, fishing festival archery, acrobatic displays and many movement of the likes were in place. it is also pertinent to say that during the season of Ochobo, of Idoma speaking area of Benue state, Nigeria, their Eja — Alikwu (i.e. a yearly festival) usually holds in the month of April, during Easter season and that people would travel from far and near with their cultural dances, and different masquerade for the celebration which usually may last for one week in a friendly and generous behavior towards visitors, people exchange gifts because that is the avenue to meeting those friends and relations one has longed to see. This varies from locality to locality in Nigeria.

Furthermore, it is necessary to emphasize that people can only struggle well and think properly when they are mentally sound and physically fit. Suleiman (2016),

added that it is important to remember that whatever people acquire and possess in this world is of little or no value to them when they do not have good health. It is possible for a person to be alive even when they may not have good health. it is possible for a person to be alive even when his/her health is poor, but life cannot be full and meaningful without good health. Meanwhile, in the individual's daily activities, the individual would need some rest and relocation: and during holidays would need to travel to relax, enjoy nature, get acquainted with new environment refresh ourselves, be Physically and mortally sound and fit again arid to re urn to 9ur work happily, refreshed and rejuvenated. Therefore, the purpose of tourism leisure and recreation activities is of- fundamental importance to punish human beings with experiences that would assist them in achieving a better state of well-being and which are bisected towards the individual's total development.

Concept of Tourism and Leisure

Tourism is the desires to enjoy leisure in a different environment; one vet itch perhaps, is beautiful and has a good climate. It is recreating outside a person's usual environment, which is deliberate and planned for the move of pleasure. Business trips, religious nips, hips made to visit friends or relatives are also part of tourism, the attraction of seeing famous paintings, and making new friends as well as seeing places and buildings are also improving lectors of tourism. Davison (1998) sees tourism as the movement people outside their normal routine for business, pleasure or personal reason. The World. Tourism Organization (WTO) also explains tourism as comprising the activities of persons traveling to and staying in places outside their I environment -for not more than one consecutive year of leisure, business other purposes' (V/TO, 1997). It is also an act of travel for recreation and the provision of services for the act.

Litton (1974, as cited in. Suleimnan, 2016) maintains that tourism is as the world known rock, adding that it started with the early i-nan, and when Adam and Eve moved out of the Garden of Eden in search of shecht and food, unknown to them, they were involved in tourism. This is because tourism is movement of' people in a quest for Pleasure. In the submission on what tourism is, Bamnhamt and Modlik (1991), stated tourism is multifaceted with. the technical elements of movements of travel stay, activities engaged. upon and the psychological impact/experience

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A layman can simply define tourism as travel and service to travelers, but tourism is far more than that; as it includes relationships and interactions of tounst businesses the word over. The world tourism Organization (2002) in a different form, describes tourism as the temporal, short term movement 01 people to destinations outside the places where they normally live and wor1 and includes all movements that do not last more than a year. Therefore, tourism is about providing facilities and infrastructure for visitors from all over the world, whether they come for spots, meetings, conferences, and or leisure. The study of tourism is therefore the study of people away from their usual habitat, of the establishments, which respond to the requirements of travelers, and of the impacts that they have on the economy, physical and social wellbeing of their hosts (Matheison, 1982). In addition, it involves the expectations and adjustment made by the residents of reception areas and the roles played by numerous agencies and institutions which intercede between them.

Leadley (1992), also viewed tourism as a system involving the discretionary travel and temporary stay of persons away from their usual places of residence for one or more nights, except tours made for primary purpose of earning remuneration from an employer. The elements of the system are tourism, generating regions, transit routes, destination regions and a tourism industry. These five elements are an-anged in social and Emotional connections. Having the characteristics of an open system, the five elements operate within broader environment, that is, physical, cultural, social, economic, and political and technical, with which it interacts. The United Nations (1992), in its definition adopted tourism as the sum of the phenomena and relationships arising from the interaction of tourism, business suppliers, host governments and host communities in the process of attracting and hosting these tourists and other visitors. McConnell (1996), in this own way,

focuses on the nature of the experience of a tourist; and that it is the expectation of having some experience of otherness". Urry (1990), described experiences which are different from those typically encountered in everyday life even though the world Tourism Organization (WTO) defined a tourist as any person residing within a country irrespective of nationality, traveling to a place other than his usual place of residence for a purpose other than the exercise of a remunerated activity in the place visited(WTO, 1985). The motive for

such travels, as further classified by WTO (1995), may be: (i) recreation, holidays, health, studies religion or sports; (ii) business, family, mission or meeting. An analysis of the above definitions reveals the following common basic elements: (a) tourism is temporary and short, (b) it involves non-residents travelling along transit routes to and from a destination, (c) varied impacts are made at the destination and the transit routes; and (i) it may be for a variety of reasons such as leisure or business, (ii) the character of the tourist may be influenced.

In a related development, the world Tourism Organization (WTO), the major inter-governmental body concerned with tourism, has led the way in establishing a set of definitions for Travel and Tourism statistics in Canada, a set of resolutions and recommendations relating to tourism concepts, definitions and classification that were adopted, as follows: (1) tourism includes among others, the activities of a person traveling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes; (2) tourist (overnight visitor) stays at least one night in a collective or private accommodation in the place visited; (3) same day visitor (excursionist) does not spend the night in a collective or private accommodation in the place visited; (4) travelled includes a person on a trip between two or more locations (WTO, 1995).

Furthermore, there are two forms of tourism at any level, in relation to any given area, for example, domestic region, country or group of countries. While domestic tourism involves residents of a given area travelling (as visitors) only within that area the inbound tourism involves travelling to an area other than the given area. Some other categorizations according to WTO (1995) are: (i) internal tourism which comprises domestic and inbound tourism and (ii) national tourism which is domestic and outbound tourism. Bhatia (2001) explains tourism as the sum total of operations, mainly of an economic nature, which directly relate to the entry, stay

and movement of foreigners inside and outside ascertain country city or regions and that further involves: (a) short travel, at least for one day not more than a year, (b) it covers expenditure on transport, accommodation, purchase and services, from when the visitor-leaves home, until he/she returns, and (c) it also includes the impact of such visits and activities on the socio-economic, political and physical environment of the host communities and visitors themselves. However, in Suleiman (2010) opinion, tourism is the sum of phenomena and relationships arising from travel and non-residents, provided that the journey does not lead to permanent residency and is not connected with any earning activity. Tourism journey also is one that entails in the history of the location, the architecture and cultural history. Generally, a tourist is a person who undertakes a journey outside his/her place of abode during his/her free and unobligated time. The free time may include weekends, annual leave or public holidays, for duration of not less than 24 hours. During such a journey, the vacationer must not undertake any remunerative employment.

Concept of Leisure

Leisure is referred to, by many professionals such as psychologists and sociologists as a time frame. It is an individual's discretionary time, where the individual is not working or studying, but time judiciously used for recreational activities, it is an individual's free time, it is spent when one wishes to spend it as she/he likes or pleases. It is an unobligated time and a period not used for official meeting or assignment. It is time spent away from all kinds of work. Leisure time activities are referred to as re-creation which is defined by Kackson (2006) as an act of experience selected by a reason during leisure to meet a personal want or desire, primarily for his or her own satisfaction, Leisure is the re-creative activity that will bring about the renewal of spirit, soul and body activities that have the potential for enrichment of life through the development of the intellect. Leisure has multiple meanings, based on an individual's perceptions. Leisure from an individual's perspective involves watching television, attending an opera, base jumping, mowing the lawn, gardening, and engaging in some physical activities among others. Leisure is concerned with recreating. It is opposed to activities that are harmful to a person or the society, physically, socially and otherwise (Bucher and Bucher, 1974; Kraus, 1966). The aim of leisure's to rest and rejuvenate, and rebuild the body from a breakdown situation. The re-build of the body from

breakdown situation, the re-building up process through leisure time activities does not end with the physical body, but extends to the mental component of the individual, and thereby enabling him/her to achieve a balanced life. It is a common knowledge that a greater percentage of Nigeria population lacks leisure habit! culture. According to Okoroafor (1993), leisure “by definition and its contemporary concept and practice is however alien to the Nigerians’ primal culture” even though Ramey and Francis (2007), opined that leisure is the time spent on activities that provide direct enjoyment.

Leisure of free time could be referred to as time spent away from business, work, domestic chores and education. It also excludes time spent on necessary activities such as eating and sleeping. Tavinghurst (1957) cited in Suleiman (2006), also explained leisure as a period that includes categories of activities. A person works in the gardens, helps around the house, engages in activities of favour for neighbors, works for the trade union, the party, the community center, all of which are devoid of monetization. These (according to him) are often called non-work obligations and they yield leisure like satisfaction. Ogunwuyi (1998), also sees leisure as free time from paid work, as well as from activities which are either obligatory, compulsory or which sustains life. Leisure according to him has always existed; and therefore, what is true is the fact that duration of free time has always been different for different people. Thus, free times come to different people at different times of the day, at specific times of the week and specific periods of the season or year.

Stebbins (1992) defines serious leisure as the systematic pursuit of an amateur, hobbyist or volunteer activity that is sufficiently substantial and interesting for a participant to find a career there in the acquisition and expression of its special skills and knowledge. He further posited that serious leisure is distinguished by six distinct qualities. First, significant personal effort is expended to acquire pertinent skills and knowledge. Secondly, the participant perseveres in spite of injuries, fatigue, bad weather and other destructors. Thirdly, participation is viewed as career. Fourth, it is a strong identification with the activity, demonstrated by excitement and frequent mention of it in conversation. Fifth, there is the development of sub-culture with its relevant values, beliefs, norms, events, moral principles, traditions and performance standards. Finally, several long lasting benefits such as self-actualization, self-enrichment, and self-expression, feelings of

accomplishments and enhancement of self-image, social interaction and physical fitness are experienced.

Organized leisure programmes have been increasing in popularity and diversity, the world over. People mostly enter organized leisure activities and programmes for a variety of reasons. The most important are to have fun, develop skills, feel the excitement and challenges of competition, be with friends and obtain fitness, achievement and status. It is also for pursuing interest; and for others, leisure becomes an integral part of their lives. The word 'leisure' evokes different thoughts and images. Normative denotations of the word have been usually expressed in terms of free time of activity or state of mind. Other scholars, who are critical of this concept, related leisure from a critical perspective to emancipatory action, participatory democracy and community development. However it should be noted that the definitions of leisure impact on how recreation practitioners conceptualize and implement service (Suleiman, 2006). Although many scholars have addressed the meaning of leisure in people's lives) the idea that leisure is what it is to people is what the public relations and advertising executives say it is. An average person does not care whether the activities are recreational, leisure expression, exercise play, or a state of mind. Therefore, any definition of leisure services should be on the basis of the public's understanding of leisure and develop product and services that capitalize on the reinforcement of the public's perception of leisure (Suleiman, 2016).

Recreational experts recently suggested that leisure should be defined and operationalized as an objective phenomenon (Mannel & Kleiber, 1997). As an objective phenomenon, leisure is conceived as an activity or set of activities, held or done in a particular setting like a beach or specific time period, and is measured through time-budgets or activity inventories. As a subjective phenomenon, leisure is operationalized as mental experiences of an individual while engaged in leisure activities and the satisfaction or meaning derived from these involvements. As a subject phenomenon, leisure also has been operationalized externally, as well as internally. From internal vantage point, scholars used the definitional approach to apply the criteria people use to define the experiences as leisure of Recreation and Leisure Activities

Some of the general recreation and leisure activities that people can select in order to recreate actively or passively, individually or in group, irrespective of gender or age, include the following:

- (i) active games and Sports: Cycling, polo, horse riding,
 - (ii) individual and dual games: lawn tennis, table tennis, hantmton, squash, swimming, jogging,
 - (iii) team games: basketball, soccer, volleyball, handball, etc
 - (iv) social activities: dancing, drafts, ayo, ludo, card games, monopoly, partying, etc
 - (v) music: singing, listening to music, going to musical concerts, etc
 - (vi) nature and outing activities: Driving for pleasure, excursion, camping, raising animals, gardening, boating, etc
 - (vii) art and craft Woodwork, metal work, pottery, basketry, embroidery, sewing, etc
 - (viii) other language-related activities: Debate, reading, listening to radio/television, public lectures, and (ix) service activities: Red Cross, etc
- (Ogunwuyi, 1998)

In further corroboration, Boateng (1986 as cited in Suleiman, 2016) also identified the following as recreational and leisure activities that people generally engage in at will: (a) communication: writing, speaking, debating, leading, etc (b) dance traditional and modern dancing, (c) drama: plays, puppetry, storytelling, (d) music: Singing, or/and listening to traditional and modern music, records, radio and television, (e) social recreation: parties, club, association affairs, (f) special events: festivals, carnivals, exhibitions, celebrations or ceremonies, like marriage, naming, burial, and (g) sports and games: tag games, draught, swimming, tennis, basketball, wrestling, boxing (Suleiman, 2016); even though, in an earlier study, the Nigerian tourism and recreational materials that attract and motivate people to recreate and travel on tour were categorized thus: (i) natural: playgrounds, rocks, mountains, waterfalls, hills, rivers, oceans, forests, animals, bushes, spring, (ii) traditional: drums, walls, mats, sticks, ropes, tents, wells, boats, hooks, shrines, (iii) modern: Stadiums, parks, museums, hostels, hotels, halls, palace, markets, cinemas, theatres, gardens, (iv) publications: books, magazines, journals, newspapers, mimeographs, pamphlets, and (v) communication: radio, television sets, videos, telephones, microphones, computers, cameras (Suleiman, 2010)

Health Benefits of Tourism and Leisure

Health could be seen as the mental state of an individual. Health is also refer to as the state of being physically, mentally, socially and spiritually healthy and sound. Health, according to the Oxford Advanced learner 's Dictionary (6th Edition) of current English cited in Denga (2015) is in the condition of person's body or mind, which could be in poor; good, excellent or the best of health. As perceived health experts however, health is wealth, while the individual allows himself time every day for privacy, quiet and introspection, get enough sleep, stretch his body if tired is part of health fitness. Taking holiday, especially annual leave for tourism and leisure to recreate activities and exercises ones' body often produces good results and makes the individual to be more productivity since after refi-eshment, our boodles are meant to move and not to remain stationary. As operationalized by Denga (2015) and Edet (2015), health benefits from tourism, leisure and recreational activities include the following:

(1) Regular/seasonal tourism and leisure is necessary for individual fitness and good health for long life and vitality while touring round and meeting good friends also change the individual life styles; and as we all learn fTom other people's culture it make us to be healthy and lively to fulfilling life and reduce the risk of depression, stress, tension,

(2) Tourism and leisure gives life satisfaction and quality of life. These two concepts are tied to successful living. It is the perception of how satisfied we are with life, and the quality of our life that accounts for a positive or negative feeling about life experiences. It is the daily activities chosen or not chosen that makes up our life experiences. Activity here is defined as being purposeful, and having an expected outcome. It may also be incorporated into one's routine, and performed unconsciously or deliberately. Activity is performed to pass the time, satisfy our interests and or fulfill our experiences and responsibilities. Elements of both play and work may occur in many activities.

(3) A life-changing experience or activity is a process which when undertaken by an individual has the ability to alter his/her life or circumstances in a substantial way. One of such activities is leisure. If people quest for a meaningful life, these Tourism and Leisure - generated pathways seem to simultaneously involved

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(4) Tourism and Leisure promotes, facilitates and enables transformation. Leisure holds infinite possibilities for changes. As an expression of individual interests, often reflecting broader social and cultural values, leisure provides individuals, communities and nations with enlarged opportunities to choose desirable life pursuits. Tourism and Leisure can serve as a well spring for the generation of new creative perspective for living one’s life. As such, leisure is an optional medium of transformation. Leisure provides opportunities for individuals to discover, explore and create new ideas in response to the need for transformation. Leisure provides opportunities for family development, relationship building and community building. Tourism and Leisure provides social benefits such as shared experiences, intimacy and emotional closeness, and cooperation and collaboration (Edet, 2015). good health. Meanwhile, in the individual’s daily activities, the individual would need some rest and relocation: and during holidays would need to travel to relax, enjoy nature, get acquainted with new environments, refresh ourselves, be physically and mortally sound and fit again and to return to our work happily, refreshed and rejuvenated. Therefore, the purpose of tourism! leisure and recreation activities is of fundamental importance to provide human beings with experiences that would assist them in achieving a better state of well-being; and which are bisected towards the individual’s total development.

Concept of Tourism and Leisure

Tourism is the desire to enjoy leisure in a different environment, one which perhaps, is beautiful and has a good climate. It is recreating outside a person’s usual environment, which is deliberate and planned for the purpose of pleasure. Business trips, religious trips, trips made to visit friends or relatives are also part of tourism. The attraction of seeing famous paintings, and making new friends as well

as seeing places and buildings are also important factors of tourism. Davison (1998) sees tourism as the movement of people outside their normal routine for business, pleasure or personal reasons. The World Tourism Organization (WTO) also explains tourism as comprising the activities of persons traveling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year of leisure, business or other purposes (WTO, 1997). It is also an act of travel for recreation and the provision of services for the act.

Litton (1974, as cited in Suleiman, 2016) maintains that tourism is as old as the world known rock, adding that it started with the early man, and that when Adam and Eve moved out of the Garden of Eden in search of shelter and food, unknown to them, they were involved in tourism. This is because tourism is movement of people in a quest for pleasure. In their own submission on what tourism is, Barnhart and Modlik (1991), stated that tourism is multifaceted with the technical elements of movements of travel, stay, activities engaged upon and the psychological impact experience it entails. Thus, when measured, results in major significant affects which bring about generation of income, foreign exchange to help balance of payment problems, regional development, creation of goodwill, peace, socio cultural promotion, enrichment and general development.

A layman can simply define tourism as travel and service to travelers, but tourism is far more than that; as it includes relationships and interactions of tourist businesses the word over. The world tourism Organization (2002) in a different form, describes tourism as the temporal, short term movement of people to destinations outside the places where they normally live and work and includes all movements that do not last more than a year: Therefore, tourism is about providing facilities and infrastructure for visitors from all over the world, whether they come for sports, meetings, conferences, and or leisure. The study of tourism is therefore the study of people away from their usual habitat, of the establishments, which respond to the requirements of travelers, and of the impacts that they have on the economy, physical and social wellbeing of their hosts (Matheison, 1982). In addition, it involves the expectations and adjustment made by the residents of reception areas and the roles played by numerous agencies and institutions which intercede between them.

Leadley (1992), also viewed tourism as a system involving the discretionary travel and temporary stay of persons away from their usual pieces of residence for one or more nights, except tours made for primary purpose of earning remuneration from an employer. The elements of the system are tourism, generating regions, transit routes, destination regions and a tourism industry. These five elements are arranged in social and functional connections. Having the characteristics of an open system, the five elements operate within broader environment, that is, physical, cultural, social, economic, and political and technical, with which it interacts. The United Nations (1992), in its definition adopted tourism as the sum of the phenomena and relationships arising from the interaction of tourism, business suppliers, host governments and host communities in the process of attracting and hosting these tourists and other visitors.

McConnell (1996), in this own way, focuses on the nature of the experience of a tourist; and that it is the expectation of having some experience of "otherness". Urry (1990), described "otherness" as experiences which are different from those typically encountered in everyday life even though the world Tourism Organization (WTO) defined a tourist as any person residing within a country Respective of nationality, traveling to a place other than his usual place of residence for a purpose other than the exercise of a remunerated activity in the place visited (WTO, 1985). The motive for such travels, as further classified by WTO (1995), may be: (i) recreation, holidays, health, studies religion or sports; (ii) business, family, mission or meeting. An analysis of the above definitions reveals the following common basic elements: (a) tourism is temporary and short, (b) it involves non-residents travelling along transit routes to and from a destination, (c) varied impacts are made at the destination and the transit routes; and (i) it may be for a variety of reasons such as leisure or business, (ii) the character of the tourist may be influenced.

In a related development, the world Tourism Organization (WTO), the major inter-governmental body concerned with tourism, has led the way in

establishing a set of definitions for Travel and Tourism statistics in Canada, a set of resolution and recommendations relating to tourism concepts, definitions and classification that were adopted, as follows: (1) touring

includes among others, the activities of person traveling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes; (2) tourist (overnight visitor) stays at least one night in a collective or private accommodation in the place visited; (3) same day visitor (excursionist) does not spend the night in a collective or private accommodation in the place visited; (4) travelled includes a person on a trip between two or more location (WTO, 1995).

Furthermore, there are two forms of tourism at any level, in relation to any given area, for example, domestic region, country or group of countries. While domestic tourism involves residents of a given area travelling (as visitors) only within that area the inbound tourism involves travelling to an area other than the given area. Some other categorizations according to WTO (1995) are: (i) internal tourism which comprises domestic and inbound

tourism and (ii) national tourism which is domestic and outbound tourism. Bhatia (2001) explains tourism as the sum total of operations, mainly of an economic nature, which directly relate to the entry, stay and movement of foreigners inside and outside ascertain country city or regions and that further involves: (a) short travel, at least for one day not more than a year, (b) it covers expenditure on transport, accommodation, purchase and services, from when the visitor-leaves home, until he/she returns, and (c) it also includes the impact of such visits and activities on the socio-economic, political and physical environment of the host communities and visitors themselves. However, in Suleirnan (2010) opinion, tourism is the sum of phenomena and relationships arising from travel and non-residents, provided that the journey does not lead to permanent residency and is not connected with any earning activity. Tourism journey also is one that entails in the history of the location, the architecture and cultural history. Generally, a tourist is a person who undertakes a journey outside his/her place of abode during his/her free and unobligated time. The free time may include weekends, annual leave or public holidays, for duration of not less than 24 hours. During such a journey, the vacationer must not undertake any remunerative employment.

Concept of Leisure

Leisure is referred to, by many professionals such as psychologists and sociologists as a time frame. It is an individual's discretionary time, where the individual is not working or studying, but time judiciously used for recreational activities. It is an individual's free time, it is spent when one wishes to spend it as she/he likes or pleases. It is an unobligated time and a period not used for official meeting or assignment. It is time spent away from all kinds of work. Leisure time activities are referred to as re-creation which is defined by Jackson (2006) as an act of experience selected by a person during leisure to meet a personal want or desire, primarily for his or her own satisfaction, Leisure is the re-creative activity that will bring about the renewal of spirit, soul and body activities that have the potential for enrichment of life through the development of the intellect. Leisure has multiple meanings, based on an individual's perceptions. Leisure from an individual's perspective involves watching television, attending an opera, base jumping, mowing the lawn, gardening, and engaging in some physical activities among others. Leisure is concerned with recreating. It is opposed to activities that are harmful to a person or the society, physically, socially and otherwise (Bucher and Bucher 1974; Kraus, 1966). The aim of leisure is to rest and rejuvenate, and rebuild the body from a breakdown situation. The re-build of the body from breakdown situation, the re-building up process through leisure time activities does not end with the physical body, but extends to the mental component of the individual, and thereby enabling him/her to achieve a balanced life. It is a common knowledge that a greater percentage of Nigeria population lacks leisure habit! culture. According to Okoroafor (1993), leisure "by definition and its contemporary concept and practice is however alien to the Nigerians' primal culture" even though Ranney and Francis (2007), opined that leisure is the time spent on activities that provide direct enjoyment.

Leisure or free time could simply be referred to as time spent away from business, work, domestic chores and education. It also excludes time spent on necessary activities such as eating and sleeping. Havinghurst (1957) cited in Suleiman (2006), also explained leisure as period that includes categories of activities. A person works in the gardens, helps around the house, engages in activities of favour for neighbors, works for the trade union, the party, the community center, all of which are devoid of monetization. These (according to him) are often called non-work obligations and they yield leisure like satisfaction. Ogunwuyi (1998),

also sees leisure as free time from paid work, as well as from activities which are either obligatory, compulsory or which sustains life. Leisure according to him has always existed, and therefore, what is true is the fact that duration of free time has always been different for different people. Thus, free times come to different people at different times of the day, at specific times of the week and specific periods of the season or year.

Stebbins (1992) defines serious leisure as the systematic pursuit of an amateur hobbyist or volunteer activity that is sufficiently substantial and interesting for a participant to find a career there in the acquisition and expression of its special skills and knowledge. He further posited that serious leisure is distinguished by six distinct qualities. First, significant personal effort is expended to acquire pertinent skills and knowledge. Secondly, the participant perseveres in spite of injuries, fatigue, bad weather and other destructors. Thirdly, participation is viewed as career, Fourth, it is a strong identification with the activity, demonstrated by excitement and frequent mention of it in conversation. Fifth, there is the development of sub-culture with its relevant values, beliefs, norms, events, moral principles, traditions and performance standards. Finally, several long lasting benefits such as self-actualization, self-enrichment, and self-expression, feelings of accomplishments and enhancement of self-image, social interaction and physical fitness are experienced.

Organized leisure programmes have been increasing in popularity and diversity, the world over. People mostly enter organized leisure activities and programmes for a variety of reasons. The most important are to have fun, develop skills, feel the excitement and challenges of competition, be with friends and obtain fitness, achievement and status. It is also for pursuing interest; and for others, leisure becomes an integral part of their lives. The word 'leisure' evokes different thoughts and images. Nonnative denotations of the word have been usually expressed in terms of free time of activity or state of mind. Other scholars, who are critical of this concept, related leisure from a critical perspective to emancipatory action, participatory democracy and community development. However, it should be noted that the definitions of leisure impact on how recreation practitioners conceptualize and implement service (Suleiman, 2006). Although many scholars have addressed the meaning of leisure in people's lives) the idea that leisure is what it is to people is what the public relations and advertising executives say it is.

An average person does not care whether the activities are recreational, leisure expression, exercise play, or a state of mind. Therefore, any definition of leisure services should be on the basis of the public's understanding of leisure and develop product and services that capitalize on the reinforcement of the public's perception of leisure (Suleiman, 2016).

Recreational experts recently suggested that leisure should be defined and operationalized as an objective phenomenon (Mannel & Kleiber, 1997). As an objective phenomenon, leisure is conceived as an activity or set of activities, held or done in a particular setting like a beach or specific time

Period, and is measured through time-budgets or activity inventories. As a subjective phenomenon, leisure is operationalized as mental experiences of an individual while engaged in leisure activities and the satisfaction or meaning derived from these involvements. As a subject phenomenon, leisure also has been operationalized externally, as well as internally. From internal vantage point, scholars used the definitional approach to apply the criteria conic use to define the experiences as leisure.

Type of Recreation and Leisure Activities

home of the general recreation and leisure activities that people can select in order to recreate actively or passively, individually or in group, irrespective of gender or age, include the following: (i) active games and Sports: Cycling, polo, horse riding, (ii) individual and dual games: lawn tennis, table tennis, table tennis, squash, swimming, jogging, (iii) team games: basketball, soccer, volleyball, handball, etc (iv) social activities: dancing, draughts, ayo, ludo, card games, monopoly, partying, etc (v) music: singing, listening to music, going to musical concerts, etc (vi) nature and outing activities: Driving for pleasure, excursion, camping, raising animals, gardening, boating, etc (vii) art and crafts: Woodwork, metal work, pottery, basketry, knitting, sewing,

listening to radio/television, public lectures, and (ix) service activities: Red Cross, scouts, girls guide (Ogunwuyi, 1998).

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will: (a) communication: writing, speaking, broad casting, reading, etc. (b) dance: additional dancing, modern dancing, (c) drama: plays, puppetry, storytelling, (d) music: Singing, or/and listening to traditional and modern music, records, radio and television, (e) social recreation: parties, club, association affairs, (f) special events: festivals, carnivals, exhibitions, celebrations or ceremonies, like marriage, naming, burial, and (g) sports and games: tag games, draught, swimming, tennis, basketball, wrestling, boxing (Suleiman, 2016); even though, in an earlier study, the Nigerian tourism and recreational materials that attracts and motivates people to recreate and travel on tour were categorized thus: (i) natural: playgrounds, iocks, mountains, waterfalls, hills, rivers, oceans, forests, animals, bushes, spring, (ii) traditional: drums, walls, mats, sticks, ropes, tents, wells, boats, hooks, shrines, (iii) modern: Stadia, parks, museums, hostels, hotels, halls, palace, markets, cinemas, theatres, gardens, (iv) publications: books, magazines, journals, newspapers, mimeographs, pamphlets, and (v) communication: radio, television sets, videos, telephones, microphones, computers, cameras (Suleiman, 2010)

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building. Tourism and Leisure provides social benefits such as shared experiences, intimacy and emotional closeness, and cooperation and collaboration (Edet, 2015).

(5) Tourism and Leisure may be the most important in life for realizing relaxation, it can reduce one's risk of major illnesses, such as heart disease, stroke, diabetes and cancer by up to 50% and lower one's risk of early death by up to 30% (percent). It's free, easy to take and has an immediate effect on people, and one does not need a GP to get some.

Tourism and Leisure is the miracle cure we have always had, but for too long we have neglected to take our recommended dose. Our health is now suffering as a consequence of ignorant.

Counselling Implications

Counselling is a branch of psychological programme which aims at giving help to individual with important information about tourism and leisure. The counsellors have a lot to do in bringing the awareness to the clients through seminars, workshops, conferences, individual and group counseling in the following: (i) giving clients information about tourism and leisure its needs and usefulness for healthy living; (ii) encourage Nigerians to take holidays and go on tour to visit friends, relations, (iii) informing clients about the benefits accruable from tourism and leisure; (iv) to inform clients about some tourism attractions in Nigeria for those who cannot afford to travel abroad; for example, in Benue state the Idoma (Ochobo), new yam and Eja-Alikwu celebration is every first week of April yearly or Tiv day celebration this vary from place to place; (v) inform the clients about sport tourism that are available in their touring such as golf; soccer, wrestling, music, dancing, and singing. Nigerians are spoil lovers and can engage in recreational spoil activities during their leisure time. Counselors can give them orientation service too.

Conclusion

This paper has taken a broad outlook at the concept of tourism and leisure; it's categories from outdoors view point, while its health benefits were also highlighted as part of a state of optimal well-being that contributes to good life. It emphasizes that a healthy life style is important for everybody, and that tourism and leisure has

a great effect on the human lives, it canvassed that the professional counsellors have lots of roles in informing and articulating the multi-dimensional benefits inherent in tourism and leisure activities for all and sundry. Therefore, tourism and leisure seminars are essential for [Second .Edition/

ai man development and healthy living; and that the counsellors should act is hrtdge for the dissemination of its benefits between the government ucneies whether at the federal, state, arid local government levels to a tceed.

suggestions/Recommendation

Urn relevance of Tourism and leisure for healthy living in Nigeria has being extensively discussed and the following recommendations and suggestions are therefore provided:

i. individuals should be encouraged to spend their holidays wisely outside their environment. It could be in oversea or within the country, depending on the individual personal saving to refresh themselves.

ii. Be wise to spend your money on tourism and leisure in order to enjoy the fruit of your labour since an adage says: “all world and no play make Jack a dull boy “.

Th. Sepante your work from leisure time, as there is time to everything, a time to rest and a time to worn.

1v. Be committed to whatever you are coting, work hard, but let your work not creep into your leisure time.

Always save ahead for your holidays, it could be in your annual leave.

vi. You can plan your holidays during the period of Christmas, Easter, Salah, workers Day, Democracy Day break etc. This is to enable you refresh and have recreating activities such as watching television, attending the movies or theatre or reading, visiting friends and relation to feel good and feel better.

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